

The Role of Thermal Expansion Mismatch on the Drying of Refractory Castables Containing Polymeric Fibers

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Abstract

The most common additive for improving the efficiency and security of refractory castables drying is the incorporation of polymeric fibers. However, the fundamental mechanisms by which they enhance water removal remain unresolved. Two main hypotheses are currently considered in the literature: (i) the formation of microcracks in the matrix surrounding the fibers during heating, due to the coefficient of thermal expansion mismatch between these two phases, and (ii) polymer melt viscous flow by the pressurized water vapor, which generates open channels increasing the permeability. The current work investigates the potential role of the thermal expansion mismatch between polymer fibers and a refractory matrix during heating, aiming to assess

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the feasibility of the first hypothesis. An analytical thermomechanical model was used to estimate the interfacial tangential stresses induced by thermal expansion differences, using temperature-dependent material properties compiled from the literature for five polymers: linear low density polyethylene (LLDPE); ultrahigh molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE); polypropylene (PP); polyamide 6,6 (PA 6,6); and polyethylene terephthalate (PET). The results indicate that the tangential stresses can reach significantly higher levels than the maximum vapor pressure induced during the heating for all polymers considered, with the highest stresses observed for PP and PA 6,6. These values suggest that the thermal expansion mismatch plays a non-negligible role in the permeability evolution during refractory castables drying, regardless of the mechanisms of permeability enhancement. A sensitivity analysis revealed that the tangential stresses are significantly influenced by the polymer's thermal expansion coefficient and the modulus of elasticity of the fiber, and of the refractory castable, which enable the search for optimal fiber properties for drying applications. When compared with experimental results in the literature, these findings support the hypothesis that thermal expansion mismatch can contribute to microcrack formation around polymeric fibers during drying, enhancing water removal from refractory castables, although more experimental investigations are under way at the moment in the authors' research group to further validate this mechanism.

Keywords: Castable drying, Polymeric fibers, Coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE), Thermomechanical modelling, Microcracking

1. Introduction

Water removal from hydraulic-bonded refractory castables is a critical step in their installation [1, 2, 3]. The evaporation of residual, unreacted water and the decomposition of hydrates generate water vapor that must be efficiently conveyed through the microstructure to avoid pressure build-up, cracking and ultimately explosive spalling [3]. This process takes place across several scales (from nano to macro ones) and is governed by strongly coupled heat and mass transport phenomena, which results in difficulties for predicting and controlling the drying process of these materials [3, 4, 5].

Due to the risk of internal vapor pressurization and explosive spalling, industrial practice often relies on long and frequently over-conservative heating schedules [6, 5]. Although these approaches mitigate the spalling risk, they do so by strongly decreasing the installation rates of these products, leading to profit losses, high energy consumption and carbon dioxide emissions [2, 3, 6, 5].

To lessen these limitations, various strategies have been developed. Numerical simulations have demonstrated great potential to predict vapor pressurization and help to design more efficient heating curves [7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 4, 12, 5, 13], although widely adopting them in the industry is hindered by the requirement of complex and transient properties, such as permeability and sorption isotherm as a function of temperature and pressure [4].

Alternative drying technologies, such as microwave-assisted heating, have also shown promising results [14, 15, 16]. Finally, modifications of the microstructure through additives — metallic powders and, most notably, polymeric fibers — to increase the overall permeability of the castable are the

most commonly adopted approach in the industrial practice [17, 18].

The latter strategy is particularly attractive because polymeric fibers are inexpensive and can introduce pathways that ease the vapor escape [17]. As illustrated schematically in Figure 1, fiber addition can generate permeable paths within the matrix, adding to the intrinsic porosity distribution of the castable, marked by regions of high permeability, called interfacial transition zone (ITZ) [19, 17]. This reduces the mass transport bottlenecks across the different scales and improves the water removal efficiency, preventing vapor accumulation and pressurization [20, 17, 21].

Figure 1: a) Schematic representation of a simplified castable pore structure. MPT is the maximum paste thickness and IPS is the inter particle separation. b) Likely paths generated by the fibers after their activation. Adapted from [19].

Despite their widespread use, attesting that they do indeed reduce the explosive spalling likelihood, the fundamental mechanisms by which polymeric fibers enhance water removal remain unresolved, as highlighted by Mohammed et al., who stated that *“The mechanism through which PP fibers*

improve the spalling behavior of concrete is still not clear, though. [22].

Two hypotheses that try to explain the observed behavior are currently considered in the literature: (i) the formation of microcracks surrounding the fibers during heating, as proposed by Zhang et al. [20] and shown in Figure 2 a), and (ii) polymer melt viscous flow by the pressurized water vapor, which generates open channels for flow, as suggested by Innocentini et al. and Salomão et al. [23, 24] and represented in Figure 2 b).

Figure 2: a) microcracks highlighted around a PP fiber in an ultra-high performance concrete and tangential stresses schematic illustrated. Adapted from [20]. b) Air flow behavior upon heating of a sample comprising PP fiber and a sample with no fiber, plus a schematic representation of the fiber state at different stages. Adapted from [23].

For the first hypothesis (**H1**), highlighted in Figure 2 a), radial microcracks would originate at the interface between the polymeric fibers and the matrix, due to the thermal expansion coefficient mismatch between these two phases and the resulting stresses on the tangential direction, $\sigma_{\theta\theta}$, [20]. In fact, microcracks could be found by scanning electron microscopy analysis of samples that were previously treated at fixed temperatures, as reported by

Zhang et al. [20]. However, it cannot be determined whether the observed microcracks were generated during drying or if they are related to sample preparation, or another unknown reason.

The second hypothesis (**H2**) is based on the correlation between the melting temperature and the increase in the relative airflow rate, shown in Figure 2 b). This hypothesis assumes that at low temperatures (from room temperature to 100°C) the fibers are present at their original positions and at the solid state, with no effect on the vapor flow. When the fiber starts to reach its melting point (165°C for polypropylene), viscous flow of the polymer induced by the vapor pressure enable the opening of paths that greatly improve the relative airflow [24]. At higher temperatures ($T > 350$ °C), the pyrolysis of the fiber would result in even higher permeability levels.

It should be noticed, however, that neither the hypothesis of the viscous flow proposed by Salomão et al. [24], nor the microcracking hypothesis can be proved or rejected due to the lack of direct evidence. Furthermore, they fail to explain certain experimental results. For instance, Bezerra et al., have shown that calcium aluminate samples comprising low density polyethylene fibers (whose melting temperature is around 105 °C) were more likely to face explosive spalling when compared with those containing polypropylene fibers [18]. A similar scenario was also observed by Zhang et al. when considering linear low-density polyethylene (LLDPE) in one-sided heating tests with pressure sensors [21].

In this case, LLDPE has both a lower melting temperature than PP (which by hypothesis **H2** should result in an earlier airflow flux increase), and a similar relative thermal expansion strain increase, because both are semi-

crystalline apolar olefinic polymers, (see Figure 3). However, for LLDPE, this thermal expansion occurs at lower temperatures. Therefore, based on **H1**, it should lead to a similar number of microcracks as in the case of PP, but at lower temperatures.

Figure 3: Linear expansion calculated from experimentally measured bulk specific volume as a function of temperature (the PVT test) for several bulk polymers and the thermal expansion of a high alumina refractory castable (5CAC).

Thus, the current work aims to investigate the role of the thermomechanical mismatch on the behavior of the permeability of refractory castable through an analytical thermomechanical model capable of estimating the tangential stresses. To do that, five polymeric fibers that were already studied in the literature [20] were considered: i) linear low-density polyethylene (LLDPE); ii) ultra-high molecular weight polyethylene (UHMWPE); iii) polypropylene (PP); iv) polyamide 6,6 (PA 6,6) and v) polyethylene terephthalate (PET).

Finally, the present investigation also aims to use the analytical thermo-

mechanical model to investigate the sensitivity of the tangential stresses that are developed at the interface between the polymeric fiber and the castable matrix to their properties and boundary conditions.

2. Background on Polymeric Fiber Molecular Structure

Polymers are made up of long chains (i.e. macromolecules) which are formed by a repeating unit [25, 26]. They can have distinct configurations (defined by the polymer's covalent bonds) and may also assume a variety of conformations depending on their chemical structure, molecular weight and processing history [25, 26].

Due to the intrinsic ordering constraints imposed by the long chains, most engineering polymers used as drying additives in refractory castables are semicrystalline materials, exhibiting a biphasic microstructure formed by amorphous and crystalline regions [26]. In the bulk state, the crystalline domains tend to organize into stacked lamellar assemblies, whereas the amorphous chain segments occupies the interlamellar space, as schematically illustrated in Figure 4 a).

During fiber production, the polymer is extruded, cooled and thus crystallized. Following that, the solid thick rod is drawn at temperatures just under their melting temperature, therefore molecular rearrangement can be induced, reorienting the lamellas by sliding the polymer chain segments, following the Peterlin crystalline reorientation model [27, 28, 29], and aligning the polymer chain segments along the stretching direction, i.e. fiber axis [26, 30]. This drawing process substantially increases molecular orientation, leading to a fibrillar morphology in which its crystalline structure is highly

oriented, as shown in Figure 4 b). This structural reorganization has a strong influence on the thermomechanical response of the polymer under heating.

Figure 4: Schematic diagrams of semi-crystalline molecular structure, a) in a bulk polymer and b) in a fiber. Adapted from [31].

Upon temperature increase, the thermal expansion of the polymer is governed by the thermal transitions of the amorphous and crystalline phases and their relative amounts. A hypothetical fully crystalline polymer would exhibit a sharp volumetric increase at the melting temperature, as shown in Figure 5 a). These schematic plots represent the results of the so-called pressure-volume-temperature test (PVT test), where the specific volume of a bulk polymer is measured during heating and under different pressure values [32].

Figure 5: Bulk specific volume as a function of temperature (PVT) for a) a theoretical crystalline polymer, b) a semi-crystalline polymer and c) an amorphous polymer.

In contrast, amorphous polymers display only smooth changes in specific volume, characterized by an increase in the thermal expansion coefficient near the glass transition temperature range [Figure 5 c)]. Semicrystalline polymers, such as those considered in this study, follow an intermediate behavior, Figure 5 b), where the melting of the crystals undergo a more gradual volume increase. If external pressure is applied during heating, the expected volumetric expansion may be reduced to an extent, but it cannot be completely eliminated.

Figure 6 shows the PVT curve of a PP bulk polymer, measured by He et al. [33]. While heating under no external pressure, the PP volume expands 10.5% when it melts. If the heating is carried out under external pressure of 200 MPa, the expansion during melting is reduced to 6.7%, but still present. This level of external pressure is significantly higher than the typical mechanical strength of refractory castables. If one considers that the melt expansion, in the vicinity of the polymeric fiber melting temperature, is only due to the degree of crystallinity of the bulk PP and independent of the morphology

of its crystals, the mentioned expansion can be assumed to present similar levels when the PP is the form of fiber, as is the present case of refractory castables. Thus, this could be a possible evidence for the microcracking at the castable matrix, while the polymer melting expansion is taking place.

Figure 6: Relative expansion of free and under 200 MPa polypropylene. Adapted from [33].

Thus, the next section introduces the set of polymers investigated in the present work, along with their main properties related to the drying of refractory castables and the thermomechanical model used to estimate the tangential stresses at the fiber-matrix interface during heating.

3. Material and Methods

3.1. Polymers Investigated in this Work

The five polymers selected in the present work, their chemical repeating units, melting temperatures and general qualitative aspects related to the drying are summarized in Table 1.

LLDPE shows the lowest melting temperature, T_m , in the selected group ranging from 120°C to 130°C. In high alumina castables, it was shown to increase the permeability earlier than PP by *in-situ* neutron tomography tests [34], although it was reported that it was not as effective as PP to prevent explosive spalling [21]. It also displayed a nonlinear behavior on the drying rate with a subsequent decrease of it [34].

The choice of UHMWPE was based on the results by Zhang et al. [20], where it was found that it did not prevent explosive spalling, and it showed a smaller thermal expansion than the other polymers investigated (the same five polymers considered in this work). It also has a higher melting temperature and a higher crystallinity degree than LLDPE, due to the very high molecular weight (lower chain ends concentration, and therefore lower free volume) and a lack of short-chain branching [35, 36].

Table 1: List of selected polymers considered in this study.

Polymer:	Repeating Unit:	Melting Temperature:	Glass Transition Temperature:	Comments:
LLDPE		120 – 130 °C	-100 °C	Lower melting temperature; increases permeability at earlier temperatures [34]; reported to be less effective than PP in preventing explosive spalling [21].
UHMWPE		~145 °C	≈ -90 °C	Higher crystallinity degree than LLDPE; second-lowest melting temperature polymer among those listed; and it could not prevent explosive spalling in the tests by Zhang et al. [20, 21].
PP		~165 °C	-10 °C	Most widely used drying-fiber additive; good performance in multiple studies [17, 18, 20, 21].
PA 6.6		250 – 265 °C	85 °C	Higher melting temperature than PP; described as effective in enhancing permeability [20, 21].
PET		~260 °C	70 °C	Higher melting temperature than PP; several authors report lower drying performance relative to polyolefins [20, 21, 17].

The choice of PP is based on its widespread use and superior performance in different studies [23, 24, 18, 17, 20, 21]. Therefore, it will be used for comparing the effectiveness of the other polymers.

Next, PA 6,6 has a melting temperature approximately 100°C higher than PP, and yet it has been shown by Zhang et al. to successfully prevent explosive spalling [20, 21]. PET, on the other hand, has a similar melting temperature to PA 6,6, but it did not show the same level of effectiveness [20, 21, 17].

These polymers span a wide range of melting temperatures, crystallinity levels and macromolecular structures, which directly affect their thermal expansion, stiffness reduction with temperature, and ultimately the thermomechanical mismatch with the castable matrix.

It should also be considered that for each polymer type, different grades and fiber manufacturing processes can lead to variations in properties such as crystallinity degree, molecular weight distribution and additives content [26, 30], which can further influence their behavior during heating.

For instance, neglecting any external pressure effects and considering that the thermal expansion of the crystalline and amorphous phases are similar, a first estimation of the volumetric expansion upon melting can be made. Based on the polymeric fibers usual crystallinity index and density of the crystalline and amorphous phases [26], the expected volumetric expansion upon melting, ΔV_{melt} , can be estimated by considering the specific volume of the semicrystalline polymer at room temperature $\bar{V}_{sc}^{T_{RT}}$, as shown in Equations 1 and 2.

$$\bar{V}_{sc}^{T_{RT}} = \frac{100 - X_c}{100} \frac{1}{\rho_a^{T_{RT}}} - \frac{X_c}{100} \frac{1}{\rho_c^{T_{RT}}} \quad (1)$$

$$\Delta V_{\text{melt}} = \frac{\overline{V}_a^{T_m} - \overline{V}_{sc}^{T_{RT}}}{\overline{V}_{sc}^{T_{RT}}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where, $\rho_a^{T_{RT}}$ is the amorphous phase density at room temperature, $\rho_c^{T_{RT}}$ is the crystalline phase density at room temperature and X_c is the expected crystallinity index of the fiber.

$$\overline{V}_a^{T_m} = \frac{1}{\rho_a^{T_m}}$$

is the specific volume of the amorphous phase at the melting temperature, T_m .

The required properties for the polymers considered in this work and the results of such analyses are summarized in Table 2. The values of degree of crystallinity marked with an asterisk were calculated from the DSC curves reported by Zhang et al. [20], using both a computational calculation of the area under the melting peaks and a manual one, measuring the weights of the printed curves.

Table 2: Estimated volumetric expansion upon melting of the selected polymers. PETG stands for polyethylene terephthalate glycol.

	LLDPE	UHMWPE	PP	PA66	PET	PETG
Amorphous phase density at T_{RT} , $\rho_a^{T_{RT}}$ (g/cm ³)		0.850	0.860	1.070		1.335
Amorphous phase density at T_m , $\rho_a^{T_m}$ (g/cm ³)	0.815	0.806	0.809	1.013		1.264
Crystalline phase density at T_{RT} , $\rho_c^{T_{RT}}$ (g/cm ³)		1.011	0.936	1.240		1.455
Fiber crystallinity index, X_c (%)	36*	80*	63*	50*	60	39*
Volume change upon melting, ΔV_m (%)	11	21	12	14	11	9

*Calculated from the DSC curves from Zhang et al. [20].

The largest expected volume expansion upon melting is observed for UHMWPE (21%), followed by PA 6,6 (14%) and PP (12%), both quite close. It is possible to see the importance of the crystallinity degree on the volumetric expansion upon melting. LLDPE, for instance, with its lower degree

of crystallinity than UHMWPE, shows a volumetric expansion of only 11% compared to the estimated value of 21% for the latter.

The interpretation of this high volumetric expansion for UHMWPE and its correlation to its poor performance reported by Zhang et al. is limited by the lack of detailed physicochemical characterization of the fibers used in their work [20, 21]. For instance, it is known that the production of UHMWPE fibers often involves the use of specific processing techniques, such as gel spinning, which can be done for different drawing ratios, leading to distinct amounts of lamellar and fibrillar crystal populations, thus showing variations in crystallinity degree, molecular orientation and the presence of residual paraffinic oil within the fiber [37]. These factors can significantly influence the thermal and mechanical behavior of the fibers during heating. Therefore, without detailed information on the specific UHMWPE fiber used in Zhang et al.'s study, it is challenging to draw definitive conclusions about their morphology and so their effectiveness in preventing explosive spalling.

This effect is also observed when comparing PET and PETG. PETG is a copolymer used for transparent bottles and it has glycol added to it to hinder crystallization, resulting in a lower crystallinity degree.

The same difficult arises during the analysis of the behavior presented when PET fibers are used. Commercial polyester fibers are available from homopolymer PET, originally developed to supply synthetic fibers to the textile industry [26]. Its crystallinity is high, producing a milkshy plastic. More recently PETG was developed, aiming the production of disposable transparent plastic bottles, which can also be processed into fiber to the less exigent fiber market [26]. It is produced by adding, during the copolymerization, a

small amount of cyclic glycol, which hinders its crystallization, resulting in a lower degree of crystallinity and so transparency [26].

As a result, PETG shows a smaller volumetric expansion upon melting (9%) compared to PET (11%). It is not explicitly stated whether the fibers used by Zhang et al. [20] were produced from standard PET or PETG. However, the relatively low crystallinity degree reported from DSC analysis (39%) suggests that the fibers were likely PETG rather than conventional PET, which could explain the lower effectiveness of these fibers in preventing explosive spalling, as reported in that work [20, 21].

It should be noted that the simplified analysis of Table 2 does not account for the influence of external pressure during heating, which can reduce the actual expansion levels, nor the effect of temperature on the elastic behavior of the polymeric fibers.

Thus, the temperature-dependent storage modulus, $E'(T)$, and thermal expansion coefficients, $\alpha(T)$, for the polymers of interest were retrieved from the literature and are presented in Figure 7. In this study, the properties for PET, not PETG, were considered. This data was used as input for the analytical model described in Section 3.2 to estimate the interfacial tangential stresses generated during heating.

The thermal expansion coefficients were calculated based on the PVT results. This approach was selected as a way to incorporate the high volumetric expansion of semi-crystalline polymers on the vicinity of their melting temperature range, which is usually not reported on the experimental data of thermal expansion. The comparison between the calculated thermal expansion and the one obtained by the PVT test is shown in Appendix C.

The balance between the decrease in $E'(T)$ and the increase in $\alpha(T)$ with temperature controls the magnitude of the resulting stresses. At low temperatures, all polymers exhibit high stiffness (on the order of 10^9 – 10^{10} Pa), but their elastic constant reduction differs significantly.

In Figure 7 a), LLDPE shows the earliest modulus drop and accelerating towards its melting temperature range (120–130 °C). UHMWPE [Figure 7 b)] displays a similar trend but maintains higher stiffness up to intermediate temperatures, consistent with its greater crystallinity degree and higher melting temperature than LLDPE. PP presents an intermediate behavior: its modulus decreases steadily but remains higher than those of the polyethylenes until reaching its melting temperature (165 °C), as shown in Figure 7 c). In contrast, PA 6,6 and PET, Figures 7 d) and e), retain much higher stiffness across the entire temperature window, showing noticeable inflection points only near their glass transitions and melting temperatures. PET, in particular, maintains a high modulus up to 90 °C (just above its glass transition temperature), reflecting the rigidity of its polymer chain due to the p-phenylene rings present in its mer (see the transition temperature values in Table 1).

Figure 7: Storage modulus and thermal expansion coefficient for a) LLDPE, b) UHMWPE, c) PP, d) PA 6,6 and e) PET bulk polymers. Adapted from [38, 39, 20, 40, 41, 42, 33, 43, 44].

Considering the thermal expansion coefficients reported in the literature (solid lines), they exhibit different trends. LLDPE and UHMWPE show the strongest increases in $\alpha(T)$ at relatively low temperatures well below its reference melting temperature T_m , due to the premature melt of defective PE crystals. This effect is better shown by the elastic modulus curve. PP also shows a significant rise in $\alpha(T)$, though shifted to higher temperatures, for the same reason as LLDPE and UHMWPE. PA 6,6 and PET display a

much lower coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) throughout most of the heating, only near their melting temperature does $\alpha(T)$ increase notably.

The expansion coefficients reported by Zhang et al. [20] (dotted lines) were defined, in a very simple manner, assuming as constant values throughout specific temperature intervals and are also shown in Figure 7. Even though some values fall on the same order of magnitude of the ones obtained by PVT, all polymers show a distinct behavior on the Zhang's reported data.

For LLDPE, the sudden increase of thermal expansion at 50 °C is not expected nor observed on the values derived from the PVT results, as shown in Figure 7 a). For UHMWPE, Figure 7 b), the thermal expansion coefficient reported by Zhang et al. was constant, even when reaching its melting temperature, where a strong increase of volume is expected and seen in the $\alpha(T)$ value from the literature, due to its high crystallinity degree. This discrepancy in behavior, which might also be associated to the distinct profiles of the other polymers reported, could be related to the configuration of the test carried out by Zhang et al. In that work, a custom non-standardized setup based on a thermomechanical analyzer was used to measure the expansion of a single fiber by placing it between two quartz discs with a touching force of 0.01 N [20, 45].

Under this configuration, the polymer is free to deform under the external force and its own weight, which can be specially problematic for UHMWPE and its abrupt stiffness reduction at T_m , due to its high crystallinity degree. Thus, the measured net strain might actually be a combination of the positive thermal strain and a negative creep one, leading to the unexpected constant behavior reported by Zhang et al.

For PP, Figure 7 c), again the increase reported by Zhang occurs at earlier temperatures and, in this case, the final values are twice the ones measured by PVT.

Furthermore, for PA 6,6, Zhang et al. reported a sudden increase at 150°C, followed by a drop at 200°C which kept constant until the fibers' melting temperature. This is an unexpected behavior, as there are no physical transformations known at this temperature range.

Finally, Zhang's results for PET show an increase of the thermal expansion coefficient much earlier than the polymer's melting point, showing no clear reason for the steep increase at 150°C.

Considering these aspects, for the thermomechanical analysis carried out in the present work the values for thermal expansions used for the polymeric fibers were based on those from the literature instead of the values measured by the adapted TMA equipment described by Zhang. et al.

Finally, the refractory castable matrix chosen to be considered in this work was represented by a high-alumina formulation (5CAC) previously studied by Moreira et al. [46, 47, 34], with the thermal expansion measured by a refractoriness under load (RUL) test (with a load of 0.02 MPa), and the elastic modulus was assumed to be equal to the one experimentally measured by Auvray et al. [48]. The 5CAC Poisson's ratio was assumed to be constant and equal to 0.2.

3.2. Thermomechanical Analytical Model

The tangential stresses resulting at the interface between an individual polymeric fiber and the refractory matrix were estimated using an analytical model adapted by Zago et al.[49], schematically represented in Figure 8.

The model considers a single cylindrical fiber embedded in an infinite elastic matrix, a simplification that can be justified by the low fiber volume fractions typically used in refractory castables (generally below 0.5 vol.%), which minimizes fiber–fiber interactions and enables the simplifying assumption of isolated inclusion behavior.

This model was selected for its straightforwardness and its suitability for assessing the fundamental mechanisms associated with CTE-mismatch induced stress development. In addition, this model has been previously validated for predicting interfacial thermomechanical stresses in real composite systems through the Digital Image Correlation technique (DIC) [49], making it an appropriate framework for quantifying the stress fields expected around polymeric fibers in refractories.

Both phases are considered as isotropic, linear elastic solids under plane-strain conditions. Displacements are defined in cylindrical coordinates, with radial (u_r) and tangential (u_θ) components as the primary variables. The tangential displacement is assumed to be zero ($u_\theta(r, \theta) = 0$). A perfect bond is assumed at the fiber–matrix interface, such that:

$$u_{r,f} = u_{r,m} \quad \text{at} \quad r = r_f \quad (3)$$

where subscripts f and m refer to the fiber and matrix, respectively. The fiber center is fixed, i.e. $u_r(r = 0) = 0$.

The radial displacement field is given by:

$$u_r(r) = \begin{cases} A_f r & \text{if } r \in \Omega_f \equiv [0, r_f] \\ A_m r + \frac{B_m}{r} & \text{if } r \in \Omega_m \equiv (r_f, \infty) \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

Figure 8: Analytical thermomechanical model, a) representation of the problem, b) description of the domain in polar coordinates. Adapted from [49].

The constants A_f , A_m and B_m are defined as:

$$A_f = \frac{\Delta T \left(\alpha_f (3\lambda_f + 2\mu_f) + \alpha_m (3\lambda_m + 2\mu_m) \frac{\mu_m}{\lambda_m + \mu_m} \right)}{2(\lambda_f + \mu_f + \mu_m)} \quad (5)$$

$$A_m = \frac{\alpha_m (3\lambda_m + 2\mu_m) \Delta T}{(2\lambda_m + 2\mu_m)} \quad (6)$$

$$B_m = \left(\frac{\Delta T \left(\alpha_f (3\lambda_f + 2\mu_f) + \alpha_m (3\lambda_m + 2\mu_m) \frac{\mu_m}{\lambda_m + \mu_m} \right)}{2(\lambda_f + \mu_f + \mu_m)} \right) r_f^2 \quad (7)$$

$$- \left(\frac{\alpha_m (3\lambda_m + 2\mu_m) \Delta T}{(2\lambda_m + 2\mu_m)} \right) r_f^2$$

where α_f and μ_f are the thermal expansion coefficient and the shear modulus (second Lamé parameter, which is obtained by $\mu_i = \frac{E_i}{2(1+\nu_i)}$) of the fiber, respectively, α_m and μ_m the elastic properties of the matrix, r_f the fiber radius and λ_f the first Lamé parameter ($\lambda_i = \frac{E_i \nu_i}{(1+\nu_i)(1-2\nu_i)}$, where E is the Young modulus and ν is the Poisson's ratio of phase i).

The interfacial tangential stresses induced when a temperature variation ΔT is applied - which are responsible for the nucleation and propagation of radial cracks - can be directly calculated as:

$$\sigma_{\theta\theta}(r_f) = (\lambda_m + 2\mu_m) \left(A_m + \frac{B_m}{r_f^2} - \alpha_m \Delta T \right) \quad (8)$$

$$+ \lambda_m \left(A_m - \frac{B_m}{r_f^2} - 2\alpha_m \Delta T \right)$$

The temperature increase was set from room temperature (25°C) up to the fiber's melting point, and it was varied step-wise in 5 °C constant increments. Using the properties retrieved from the literature (Appendix A), upper-bound estimates of interfacial tangential stress, $\sigma_{\theta\theta}(r = r_f)$, were calculated for each combination of polymeric fiber and 5CAC matrix.

Additionally, a systematic sensitivity analysis was carried out to evaluate the influence of fiber radius, elastic moduli, thermal expansion coefficients and temperature change, all assumed constant to simplify the comparison of their effects. The range of parameters investigated is summarized in Table

3.

Table 3: Summary of the properties chosen for the sensitivity analysis. The underlined values are the ones taken as the reference case.

Temperature Change	$\Delta T = [75^\circ\text{C}, \underline{150^\circ\text{C}}, 300^\circ\text{C}]$
Fiber Radius	$r_f = [20 \mu\text{m}, \underline{40 \mu\text{m}}, 80 \mu\text{m}]$
Fiber Young Modulus	$E_f = [2 \text{ GPa}, \underline{4 \text{ GPa}}, 8 \text{ GPa}]$
Matrix Young Modulus	$E_m = [13.5 \text{ GPa}, \underline{27 \text{ GPa}}, 54 \text{ GPa}]$
Fiber Thermal Expansion Coefficient	$\alpha_f = [0.75 \times 10^{-4} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}, \underline{1.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}}, 3 \times 10^{-4} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}]$
Matrix Thermal Expansion Coefficient	$\alpha_m = [6 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}, \underline{12 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}}, 24 \times 10^{-6} \text{ }^\circ\text{C}^{-1}]$
Fiber Poisson's Ratio	$\underline{\nu_f = 0.43}$
Matrix Poisson's Ratio	$\underline{\nu_m = 0.27}$

4. Results and Discussions

In this section, the analytical model previously introduced is first used to quantify the relative influence of the governing parameters on the interfacial tangential stress. Next, the temperature-dependent properties compiled for the selected polymers are used to estimate the stress evolution during heating and to discuss likely implications for the different hypothesis of the permeability enhancement mechanisms.

4.1. Sensitivity Analysis of the Analytical Model

Figure 9 summarizes the sensitivity analysis by comparing the effect of each input parameter with the reference case defined in Table 3. As expected from Equation 8, the stress magnitude scales linearly with the applied temperature change, as shown in Figure 9 a). In contrast, in Figure 9 b), the fiber radius r_f displays no influence on the predicted interfacial stress values, as $\sigma_{\theta\theta}(r_f)$ does not depend on r_f in the adopted formulation (notice that the

$\frac{1}{r_f^2}$ in Equation 8 is cancelled by r_f^2 present in the expression for B_m , Equation 7). Thus, it only changes the extent of the region under the resulting stresses.

The Young modulus impacts the stress through the Lamé parameters λ_f and μ_m . Increasing E_f or E_m - Figure 9 c) and e) - raises the stress level in a similar manner.

Among the material properties investigated, the fiber coefficient of thermal expansion exhibits the strongest influence, leading to a significant increase in tangential stresses as the fiber volumetric expansion during heating increases [Figure 9d)]. In contrast, the effect of the matrix thermal expansion coefficient is negligible, Figure 9f).

Under the plane-strain assumption, the matrix is constrained from expanding in the out-of-plane direction ($\epsilon_{zz} = 0$). Consequently, changes in α_m do not directly translate into additional deformation, even though the thermal expansion mismatch (i.e. $\alpha_f - \alpha_m$) rises. Instead, variations in α_m generate a uniform stress contribution that is incorporated into the analytical solution. This results in a partial cancellation of the terms that comprise α_m in the matrix and fiber responses, such that the interfacial tangential stress is governed primarily by the fiber thermal expansion and the elastic properties (E_m and E_f) of the two phases.

Figure 9: Sensitivity analysis for the tangential stress, separated on 6 groups comparing the effect of i) ΔT , ii) r_f , iii) E_f , iv) α_f , v) E_m , iv) α_m .

These trends are summarized in Figure 10, where the variation relative to the reference case is reported. Overall, the ranking of importance obtained here indicates that accurate temperature-dependent thermal expansion and Young modulus data for both phases are the most critical inputs for estimating mismatch-induced tangential stresses, whereas geometric variations within typical fiber diameter primarily affect the mass transport connectivity rather than the local stress amplitude.

Figure 10: Variation in the tangential stress relative to the reference case. The hatched areas indicate zero variation.

4.2. Estimated tangential stresses for the selected polymers

Using the compiled temperature-dependent properties, estimates of $\sigma_{\theta\theta}(r = r_f)$ were calculated for each polymer as a function of temperature, Figure 11 a). The observed trends reflect the competition between i) the increasing thermal strain with temperature and ii) the stiffness reduction of the polymers near their melting points.

For polyolefins (LLDPE, UHMWPE, and PP), the stress evolution is governed by the large increase in thermal expansion prior to melting, whereas the progressive reduction in modulus limits the stress growth as the melting temperature is approached, as seen in Figure 7. In contrast, PA 6,6 and PET retain higher stiffness over a broader temperature range - a consequence of their higher melting points, but their lower thermal expansion coefficients

reduce the mismatch term, resulting in a more delayed stress development (for PA 6,6) or a less marked evolution, as seen for PET.

Figure 11: a) Evolution of the tangential stress with the temperature, b) spalling behavior of UHPC samples with LLDPE, c) UHMWPE, d) PP, e) PA 6,6 and f) PET. Adapted from [21].

From this analysis, it is evident that PP and PA 6,6 are the polymers that lead to the highest tangential stresses with the temperature. This correlates with their reported effectiveness in enhancing permeability and preventing explosive spalling [20, 21], as highlighted by the results of explosion tests carried out by Zhang et al. [21], shown in Figures 11 b) and f). For these polymers, the estimated stresses are over 40 times higher than the vapor pressure calculated by the Antoine equation [Figure 11 a)].

The direct correlation of the polymer fibers used in the concrete that survived the explosion tests with the ones that generated the highest tangential stresses, combined with the fact that the thermomechanical stresses

are significantly higher than the calculated vapor pressure, suggests that the thermal expansion mismatch (i.e. the difference $\alpha_f - \alpha_m$) is a key factor for the permeability enhancement of castables comprising such additives. This also strengthens the microcracking hypothesis (**H1**).

Finally, LLDPE, UHMWPE and PET show $\sigma_{\theta\theta}(r = r_f)$ values that are lower than 60% of those of PP and PA 6,6, which correlates with their comparatively reduced effectiveness in preventing explosive spalling, as shown in the broken pieces present in the inserts b), c) and f) of Figure 11.

These results can explain the observed difference of effectiveness between LLDPE and PP fibers, as reported by Zhang et al. [20, 21], favoring the microcracking hypothesis (**H1**). Even though PP has a higher melting temperature than LLDPE, its higher crystallinity degree leads to a larger volumetric expansion upon melting (55% against 34%, see Table 2) combined with a smaller reduction on the Young modulus with temperature, resulting in higher thermomechanical stresses.

Again, the lower effectiveness of PET fibers observed in Figure 11 could be related to using PETG fibers instead of standard PET, as discussed in Section 3. In the current analysis, standard PET properties were used, which might have overestimated the thermomechanical stresses generated by the fibers.

Nonetheless, the induced stresses for all polymeric fibers are still significantly higher than the vapor pressure, indicating that even for these polymers the thermomechanical stresses can be critical to induce changes in the castable pore structure leading to permeability enhancement, when a suitable thermomechanical mismatch is designed.

This highlights the crystallinity degree as a key parameter, because it directly impacts the thermal expansion behavior, as demonstrated in Figure 5. The sudden increase in specific volume promoted by the melting of the crystalline fraction of the polymeric fibers contributes to a sharp rise in thermomechanical stresses.

Finally, the current work highlights the importance of considering the thermomechanical mismatch between polymeric fibers and the refractory matrix as a key aspect on the permeability enhancement of castables comprising fibers during drying. The method presented here and the findings can further guide the selection and design of polymer additives for improved drying performance.

5. Conclusions

The current work investigated the thermomechanical mismatch between polymeric fibers and a refractory matrix during heating, aiming to understand its potential role in the permeability enhancing mechanisms activated during the drying of fiber-containing refractory castables. An analytical thermomechanical model was used to estimate the interfacial tangential stresses induced by thermal expansion differences, using temperature-dependent material properties compiled from the literature for five polymers: LLDPE, UHMWPE, PP, PA 6,6, and PET.

The sensitivity analysis revealed that the fiber thermal expansion coefficient and Young modulus of both the matrix and the fibers are the most influential parameters affecting the interfacial stress magnitude, whereas fiber diameter had no effect on it. The temperature change and matrix properties

also impact the stress but to a lesser extent.

Using the compiled literature properties, it was found that PP and PA 6,6 generated the highest interfacial tangential stresses during heating, correlating with their reported effectiveness in preventing explosive spalling in refractory castables and concrete. The estimated stresses for all polymers greatly exceeded the vapor pressure within the castable pores, suggesting that thermomechanical mismatch-induced stresses are a critical factor in enhancing permeability.

This also corroborates with the matrix microcracking hypothesis (**H1**), as the stresses caused by the thermal expansion mismatch are higher than the water vapor pressurization during heating. Thus, the fiber thermal expansion behavior becomes a key point in the selection and design of semi-crystalline thermoplastic polymer additives for refractory castables drying.

The possibility of explaining the difference in the effectiveness of LLDPE and PP fibers also favors the microcracking hypothesis, as the current analysis showed higher stresses for the castables comprising PP fibers, even though it has a higher melting temperature than LLDPE.

Overall, the degree of crystallinity of the polymeric fibers emerges as a critical parameter, as it directly influences the thermal expansion behavior, specially during melting, and, therefore, the resulting thermomechanical stresses developed at the fiber–matrix interface.

Future work should focus on experimental validation of the predicted stress levels and their direct correlation with permeability changes during drying, such as through in-situ analysis. Additionally, using more advanced numerical models, such as phase-field ones, could provide deeper insights into

the local stress distributions and potential crack initiation sites. Finally, the analysis of the crystallinity degree on the permeability enhancement capability of different polymeric fibers can provide important information to either reinforce or question the microcracking hypothesis.

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Appendix A. References of the Properties Considered in this Work

The list of references used to compile the temperature-dependent properties of the polymers considered in this work is presented in Tables A.1, A.2 and A.3.

Table A.1: Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE) as a function of temperature and Pressure-Volume-Temperature diagrams.

Property	Polymer	Heating Rate	Reference
CTE, α [$^{\circ}\text{C}^{-1}$]	LLDPE	–	[50]
	UHMWPE	10 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$	[51]
	PP	5 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$	[52]
	PA 6,6	–	[53]
	PET	–	[54]
PVT	LLDPE	2.5 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$	[39]
	UHMWPE	–	[41]
	PP	–	[33]
	PA 6,6	–	[33]
	PET	–	[33]

Table A.2: Storage modulus as a function of temperature. 3PTB represents three-point bending tests.

Property	Material	Frequency	Heating Rate	Reference
Storage Modulus (E')	LLDPE	1 Hz (Tensile)	5 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$	[38]
	UHMWPE	1 Hz (3PTB)	5 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$	[40]
	PP	1 Hz (3PTB)	3 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$	[42]
	PET	1 Hz (Tensile)	2 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$	[44]
	PA 6,6	1 Hz (Tensile)	3 $^{\circ}\text{C}/\text{min}$	[43]

Table A.3: Poisson's ratio.

Property	Material	Value	Reference
Poisson Ratio (ν)	LLDPE	0.44	[55]
	UHMWPE	0.46	[56]
	PP	0.43	[57]
	PET	0.43	[57]
	PA 6,6	0.46	[57])

Appendix B. Summary of Cases in the Sensitivity Analysis

The cases taken for in the sensitivity analysis are summarized in Table B.4.

Table B.4: Summary of all cases in the sensitivity analysis. The values in bold show the parameters changed in relation to the reference case (Test 1).

Test	ΔT [°C]	r_f [μm]	E_f [GPa]	α_f [°C ⁻¹]	E_m [GPa]	α_m [°C ⁻¹]	ν_f	ν_m
1	150°C	20 μm	4	1.5×10^{-4}	27	6×10^{-6}	0.43	0.27
2	75°C	20 μm	4	1.5×10^{-4}	27	6×10^{-6}	0.43	0.27
3	300°C	20 μm	4	1.5×10^{-4}	27	6×10^{-6}	0.43	0.27
4	150°C	10 μm	4	1.5×10^{-4}	27	6×10^{-6}	0.43	0.27
5	150°C	40 μm	4	1.5×10^{-4}	27	6×10^{-6}	0.43	0.27
6	150°C	20 μm	2	1.5×10^{-4}	27	6×10^{-6}	0.43	0.27
7	150°C	20 μm	8	1.5×10^{-4}	27	6×10^{-6}	0.43	0.27
8	150°C	20 μm	4	7.5×10^{-5}	27	6×10^{-6}	0.43	0.27
9	150°C	20 μm	4	3.0×10^{-4}	27	6×10^{-6}	0.43	0.27
10	150°C	20 μm	4	1.5×10^{-4}	13.5	6×10^{-6}	0.43	0.27
11	150°C	20 μm	4	1.5×10^{-4}	54	6×10^{-6}	0.43	0.27
12	150°C	20 μm	4	1.5×10^{-4}	27	3×10^{-6}	0.43	0.27
13	150°C	20 μm	4	1.5×10^{-4}	27	12×10^{-6}	0.43	0.27

Appendix C. Comparison of Thermal Expansion Coefficients from the Literature and Calculated from PVT data

The thermal expansion coefficients obtained from the PVT data compiled from the literature and the ones directly reported in different works are shown in Figure C.1.

Figure C.1: Comparison between the thermal expansion coefficient obtained by PVT results and measured experimentally for a) LLDPE, b) UHMWPE, c) PP, d) PA 6,6 and e) PET polymers.